

<https://eurosciencegateway.eu>

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D 1.1 Data Management Plan

EuroScienceGateway data management and contingency management plan

Work package 1

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
API	A pplication P rogramming I nterface
CERN	C onseil e uropéen pour la r echerche n ucléaire (European Organization for Nuclear Research)
DIRAC	A community grid solution
DMP	D ata M anagement P lan
DOI	D igital O bject I dentifier
DRS	D ata R epository S ervice
EOSC	E uropean O pen S cience C loud, a grouping of infrastructure services, projects, policies and institutions, mostly within EU, that aim to support researchers for achieving Open Science and FAIR https://www.eosc.eu
ESG	E uro S cience G ateway (this project)
FAIR	F indable, A ccessible, I nteroperable, R eusable, a set of principles for scientific data management that emphasizes best practices and machine readability. https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18
GA4GH	G lobal A lliance f or G enomics and H ealth
GDPR	G eneral D ata P rotection R egulation, the EU law that establishes the legal framework for personal data management
GTN	G alaxy T raining N etwork
GUI	G raphical U ser I nterface
JSON-LD	J ava S cript O bject N otation for L inked D ata
MSCP	M uon S pectroscopy C omputational M odel
OAI-PMH	O pen A rchives I nitiative P rotocol for M etadata H arvesting
OSI	Open Source Initiative
PID	P ersistent I dentifier; a long-lasting reference to a digital resource
REST	R epresentational S tate T ransfer
RO-Crate	RO-Crate is the marriage of Research Objects with DataCrate
TES	T ask E xecution S ervice
WfExS	W orkflow E xecution S ervice backend
WP	W ork P ackage, a set of related activities within a project.

1. Executive Summary

The deliverable D1.1 – Data Management Plan – establishes the framework under which EuroScienceGateway (ESG) will generate, process and collect data during the project's activities. Moreover, it will define how the data will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use and how the data will be curated and preserved after the project is completed.

The current initial version is composed of preliminary information and frameworks that will be followed. Thus, it is subject to updates in the future upon developments and changes in the course of the project, aiming for adequate characterization of used and generated data sets. Principally, the DMP describes the standards that will be used, how the project's research data will be stored and published for verification and reuse. ESG aims for full open access to data, following the principles of FAIR¹ use. The proper connection of included raw data with workflows and results by tracking data provenance through the entire data life cycle is key.

The first section of the document presents the document's purpose in the ESG project context and includes statements on the future changes and their management.

The second section comments on underlying data, their handling, generation and future use, respecting and emphasising on FAIR principles.

The third section comprises declarations on included resources, data security and privacy as well as ethical considerations.

2. Introduction

This document serves as a Data Management Plan for the EuroScience Gateway project. It provides principles, policies and describes data as well as processes, which apply across multiple project activities. However, the digital landscape is intrinsically subject to rapid changes. Thus, this document will potentially change over time in order to include new settings, best practices and technologies into the consortium policies as they occur. Consequently, a change management is necessary and described in this chapter as well. In this chapter we provide an overview of the document's goals, relationships with other activities, and handling of changes to the data management plan.

2.1. Objective and scope

The current deliverable D1.1 – Data Management Plan – constitutes a guideline complying to European and national legislation on the acquiring, handling, processing and archiving of data generated during the EuroScience Gateway project and beyond the project's end, being updated upon influencing developments. D1.1 allows for a consortium-wide alignment around the project's data management processes. The objective is to promote the principles of:

- FAIR data management and stewardship, as described in the paper "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship" (Wilkinson *et al.* 2016²);
- the GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679);
- the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention 108 for the Protection of Individuals according to Automatic Processing of Personal Data;
- the national laws applying its provisions.

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18

Although EuroScienceGateway will not manage all data assets directly, this document establishes a set of guidelines and best practices. All participants are expected to comply in their data management activities.

2.2. Relation to other activities

As other WP1 deliverables, the DMP has a transversal actuation throughout EuroScienceGateway, providing a guideline on how partners should generate, acquire, handle, share, and curate research data during all activities carried out within and beyond the project.

The DMP will be made publicly available to ensure that the entire consortium is aware of the practices that shall be followed within the conduction of those activities.

2.3. DMP Change Management

EuroScienceGateway and its participants acknowledge how the data and IT services environment is evolving at a steady pace as Information Technology is rapidly becoming not only enabling, but essential to research.

EuroScienceGateway will therefore update the DMP upon developments of associated scientific fields and indications from consortium participants. Analogously, the distribution of notifications on updates will be realised via the regular meetings (WPs, WP leaders, Executive Board, General Assembly). Participants are committed to keep track of updates, read them and discuss contra-indicating issues. In general, changes need to be fully compliant with EU laws and best practices in scientific data management.

3. Data Summary

In this chapter we describe the various types of data the ESG consortium will handle during its operational period. Some assets will be managed directly by the ESG WPs, while others will be managed by partner projects independently. However, for the purpose of general data management, each discrete data asset should fall in one of the categories described in the present chapter and be treated accordingly.

3.1. Existing data/software and newly generated project outputs

Existing software that will be reused are listed below. All software will follow an [Open Source Initiative](#) (OSI)-approved licence model, which allows sharing and reuse. These software will be extended in order to be interconnected via the use of API.

- [RO-Crate profiles for workflow run](#)
- [WorkflowHub](https://bio.tools/workflowhub) web platform (<https://bio.tools/workflowhub>) and source code (FAIRDOME-SEEK or seek4science - https://bio.tools/seek_for_science)
- [DIRAC interware](#)
- [Pulsar API](#)
- [GA4GH Task Execution Service \(TES\) API](#)
- [Workflow Execution Service backend](#) (WfExS)
- [Galaxy software](#) and instances (such as UseGalaxy.eu)
- [Onedata software](#) and service instances/repositories offered by EGI-Foundation
- [iRODS](#) Open Source Data Management Software and service instances.
- Software tools developed by the [MSCP](#) and by the communities of [biodiversity](#), [climate change](#)

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and astrophysics

Existing data that will be reused are biodiversity, climate change and astrophysics datasets, including:

- Genomic data from [GenomeArk repository](#) (raw sequencing data, genome assemblies, genome annotations)
- [Copernicus](#) the European Union's Earth observation programme

These datasets will be used to test and prove the newly developed functionalities of the software listed above. All datasets have an OSI approved open licence that allows sharing and reuse. All datasets will be reachable through permanent links or findable through permanent/public identifiers.

New outputs generated by the project are listed below.

- RO-Crates profiles and specifications
- New features in the WorkflowHub software
- Maturity model for the deployment of national instances of the European Science Gateway
- Open Infrastructure as code (the actual configuration and deployment specification of usegalaxy.eu as code on GitHub)
- Pulsar API for the GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES) API and TES support to WfExS
- Integration point for compute resources into Galaxy account
- Extended [DIRAC](#) meta-scheduler
- Profiles used for training of the meta-scheduler
- Data analysis tools and workflows for biodiversity and climate science data
- Data and method to evaluate benefits of ESG
- Quantitative dataset, from experimental and observational studies, of astrophysical measurements
- Muon Galaxy portal
- EuroScienceGateway (ESG) website and [GTN](#) training material
- Galaxy object store plugins for Onedata integration with Galaxy

3.2. Formats of the project outputs

Open-source file formats and programming languages are widely used in ESG, as well as for existing and new software. Specifically, WorkflowHub code is mainly in Ruby (.rb), RO-Crates profiles and specifications are in JSON-LD (.jsonld), Pulsar and TES API are mostly in Python (.py), integrations with the Galaxy API are mainly done in Python, JavaScript, PHP and Java, extension of DIRAC meta-scheduler is mainly done in Python and Java. WfExS code and its software dependencies are mostly in Python (.py). The Open Infrastructure as code consists of Terraform and Ansible recipes and configuration files in YAML and JSON like formats.

Quantitative datasets for astrophysical measurements are in the format .root, which can be processed with [ROOT](#), the open source and C++ based software, widely used and developed in the High Energy Physics community.

Data and methods to evaluate benefits of ESG and the maturity model will be compiled in open tabular and text format (.txt, .md, .csv, .tsv).

3.3. Purpose of the data generation and re-use, relation to the project's objectives

Objective 1: Accessible e-Infrastructure resources for European scientists to enable pioneering data-driven research across scientific domains.

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- EuroScienceGateway will create Open Infrastructure deployments (Infrastructure as Code) of Galaxy instances to be reused by local, national and international projects.

Objective 2: Support the varieties of analysis types and diverse usage patterns through efficient and smart job distribution to appropriate and sustainable infrastructures.

- The extension of DIRAC meta-scheduler with data locality variable in Pulsar
- The integration of different storage and compute resources into the EuroScienceGateway Open Infrastructure

Objective 3: The application of FAIR principles to workflows and adoption of FAIR Digital Objects to stimulate reusable and reproducible research and enable the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

- Description of workflows executed using EuroScienceGateway as RO-Crate objects and their publication in the WorkflowHub registry

Objective 4: Adoption of the EuroScienceGateway by researchers in diverse scientific disciplines.

- Use cases from the disciplines of climate change, biodiversity, and astrophysics for testing the EuroScienceGateway and for proving its benefit

3.4. Volume of the project outputs

The expected size for software, specifications, methods, reports and related documentation is less than 20 GB.

3.5. Origin/provenance of the project outputs reused or newly generated

The generated software will extend the existing software previously developed by CERN or open communities, such as Galaxy project, ELIXIR, GA4GH and WorkflowHub community. Biodiversity, climate change and astrophysics datasets that will be reused, and which originated from experimental and observational studies.

3.6. Data utility

The output of this project, that is the ESG Open Infrastructure, can be used by any research community or infrastructure provider with the need to perform intensive data analysis on multidisciplinary data types, without relying on high technical skills in computer science.

4. FAIR data

The ESG consortium acknowledges the primary importance of data findability: if a data asset is not findable, for practical purposes it does not exist. The consortium is therefore committed to enforcing data findability.

In this section we outline the ESG policies and best practices concerning FAIR publication of research data assets. ESG is committed to the publication of research data according to the FAIR principles. ESG will document its FAIR enabling practices as part of the ELIXIR [RDMkit](#).

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Persistent identifiers

All research data assets produced within the project must be associated upon publication with a persistent and dereferenceable identifier. For public repositories we will adopt the identifiers provided by the resource. For workflows a DOI will be minted through WorkflowHub using DataCite. Outputs submitted to Zenodo, will be assigned a DOI through this service. For code we will adopt the practices of the developers community of the software we are building on.

Provided metadata for discovery

Metadata required by data repositories will be used. [Zenodo's metadata](#) is compliant with DataCite's [Metadata](#) Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments. WorkflowHub's metadata is compliant with ComputationalWorkflow Bioschemas profile, and it uses a [custom list of metadata](#) for discovery via GUI.

Search keywords for discovery

Keywords will be created and then used to tag research output in Zenodo and WorkflowHub, and in other registries or repositories (OpenAIRE and EOSC catalogue).

Metadata for harvesting and indexing

Zenodo's metadata is harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name, and is also retrievable through the public [REST API](#). WorkflowHub implements GA4GH's [Tool Registry Service API](#) to facilitate discovery of workflows in an interoperable way. WfExS implements client access to services implementing GA4GH's Tool Registry Service API (workflow fetching), [Data Repository Service API](#) (data fetching), among other standard (meta)data fetching procedures. Execution delegation on services implementing Task Execution Service API will be implemented.

4.2. Making data accessible

The ESG consortium acknowledges the importance of data accessibility: if a data asset cannot be accessed, it cannot be integrated and/or reused in any way. The consortium is therefore committed to enforcing data accessibility.

All research data assets produced within the ESG project must be published in such a way that they are accessible by others. As a general rule, ESG will consider as "accessible data" all research data assets exposed through one or more of the suiteable, public community repositories.

Repositories

All profiles, specifications, configuration files, software, workflows and code will be deposited in GitHub. Where relevant, a digital object identifier (DOI) will be assigned via publication of versions and released to Zenodo or WorkflowHub. Methods and processes will also be published in Zenodo and assigned a DOI. Therefore, the ESG will use GitHub, Zenodo and WorkflowHub as their standard and main repositories.

Availability of the project outputs

All profiles, specifications, configuration files, software, workflows and code will be made openly available before the end of the project. No embargo period will be applied.

Standardised access protocol

All data will be accessible via URL or DOI. Data in Galaxy will also be available via [GA4GH DRS](#).

There will be no restrictions on the use of the research outputs, both during and after the end of this project. People accessing the data will not need to be identified and there is no need for a data access committee.

Metadata availability

Metadata containing information to enable users to access the data will be openly available and published together with the data, same repositories as listed above.

There is no time limit on metadata and data availability.

Documentation

The ESG project acknowledges the value of documentation for interoperability purposes, increased uptake by different communities, and will encourage data owners to document their research data assets. ESG does not enforce specific provisions on documentation as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the mentioned repositories and properly curated according to the repository's best practices. Research data itself should not be considered self-documenting and each published asset must be associated with sufficient documentation resources accessible through a public URL. Documentation must be browsable and include hypertext references to facilitate its fruition. Recommended documentation formats include markdown, HTML, and other markup languages. The inclusion of machine-readable documentation such as OpenAPI where applicable is thoroughly encouraged. If a scientific publication is tied to the research data asset, the publication itself should be referenced and/or made available as part of the documentation.

Documentation for data in .root format will contain the instructions and the name of the software needed to read the data, as well as all other digital outputs. Dependencies to other open-source software will be documented.

4.3. Making data interoperable

The ESG consortium acknowledges the importance of data interoperability: if a data asset cannot be compared, merged, or otherwise integrated with other assets, then its publication would bring little or no value to the community. The consortium is therefore committed to support in and enforcing data interoperability. The underlying Galaxy framework is offering numerous interoperability features that simplifies data integration on the framework level and with ESG we will develop this further.

Data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats and methodologies

The following standards will be used to make the project outputs interoperable and reusable: OpenAPI, RO-Crate and GA4GH.

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The EDAM ontology³ will be used for annotation of tools and resources, and of workflows in WorkflowHub.

Qualified references⁴ to other data

Technical dependencies between codes or software and links between datasets will be explicitly described, and proper citations (including globally unique and persistent identifiers) will be provided.

4.4. Increase data re-use

How documentation will be provided

A description of the output deposited in Zenodo will be provided in the appropriate metadata field. Documentation as README files will also be stored in GitHub and WorkflowHub, together with the code. Documentation will also be shared via Galaxy Community Propeller onboarding cookbook.

Additional information about how to test, build, deploy and install the new features added to the software will be added to the existing documentation (for users, for developers). Release notes will be attached and published together with the release. Git and GitHub will be used as version control systems. Training material will be provided via GitHub and will be kept up to date by the Galaxy community.

Licences

The ESG project is committed to promote the usage of licences that are broad and permissive in scope, allowing for a wide take-up of publications and therefore easing the spreading of scientific knowledge throughout the research community, and beyond, in compliance with the EU indications and Horizon Europe program recommendations and obligations.

Data assets to be published within the ESG project will therefore follow the following licensing scheme: All software and digital output will be licensed using standard OSI-approved licences. For instance, the WorkflowHub code (seek4science - biotools:seek_for_science) has a BSD [3-clause](#) license.

Data produced in the project can be usable by third parties both during and after the end of the project.

Documentation of provenance of the data

ESG considers data provenance information instrumental as it facilitates the expression of scientific objectives and protocols to be implemented while respecting the framework of requirements and respecting the rules of ethics and data management.

In compliance with all the requirements of the FAIR principles, a version number will be assigned to each release of the software or code, in order to capture provenance. Provenance information will also be included in RO-Crates profiles, which are easily exportable by the developed framework.

³ <https://edamontology.org/page>

⁴ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Other research outputs

All the questions pertaining to the application of FAIR principles to the management of the software and other research outputs reused and/or generated by this project have been answered in each section.

5. Resources, Security and Ethics

5.1. Allocation of resources

Costs for making data or other research outputs FAIR

Making data FAIR will not result in any additional costs, because we will use resources available in participating institutes or free to use platforms and software, such as GitHub, WorkflowHub, DataCite and Zenodo.

Responsibilities for data management

The project Management Board will be responsible for the data management.

Long term preservation of project outputs

GitHub, Workflowhub, DataCite and Zenodo are preserving data and metadata for long-term preservation without costs for the ESG. For GitHub there is an additional safeguard through the copy stored by the Software Heritage⁵.

The project Management Board will decide what data will be kept for the long term.

5.2. Data security

Trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation

GitHub, Workflowhub and Zenodo could preserve data and metadata for long-term preservation without costs. Data stored during data analysis at the developed Galaxy services are stored, backed up and recovered following the associated data policy of the attached computing facility.

5.3. Ethics

There are no ethics nor legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing in this project.

Informed consent for data sharing is not applicable to this project data and output.

⁵ <https://www.softwareheritage.org>